

Development of Generalized QSAR Models for Predicting Cytotoxicity and Genotoxicity of Metal Oxides Nanoparticles

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, nanomaterials have gained tremendous attention due to their wide variety of industrial applications including food packaging, consumer products, nanomedicines, etc. The fascinating properties of nanoparticles which are responsible for creating several exciting opportunities, however, are also accountable for growing concerns of their toxic effects on humans as well as the environment. Thus, in the present study, the authors have developed generalized models for predicting the cytotoxicity and genotoxicity of seven metal oxide nanoparticles. The models not only take into account the structural features, but also the diverse experimental conditions under which the toxicity of nanoparticles was determined. The diverse experimental conditions were captured in the generalized models using the Box-Jenkins moving average approach. Here, two machine learning techniques, namely, linear discriminant analysis and random forest were utilized to build the final models. Importantly, the validation metrics showed that the developed models have significant discriminatory power.

KEYWORDS

Box-Jenkin's Approach, Health Hazard Assessment Linear Discriminant Analysis, Machine Learning, Multi-Tasking Classification Models, NanoQSAR, Random Forest

INTRODUCTION

Nanotechnology is a branch of science and engineering that involves the manipulation of matter with at least one dimension sized from 1 to 100 nanometers (Jeevanandam, Barhoum, Chan, Dufresne, & Danquah, 2018). Nanomaterials or nanoparticles, due to their small sizes in nanometer range have

DOI: 10.4018/IJQSPR.20201001.0a2

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fascinating properties that widely vary from the corresponding bulk material. Thus, in recent years, the nanomaterials have gained a prominent status due to their diverse applications in several fields such as food packaging, medicines, electronics, consumer products, optical devices, *etc.* (Özogul, McClements, Kosker, Durmus, & Ucar, 2019). However, along with the exciting opportunities, there have been growing concerns regarding the risks of nanomaterials on the environment as well as human health (Jeevanandam et al., 2018). For instance, the nanomaterials used in consumer products like pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, powdered food, *etc.* are anticipated to end up into aquatic, and/or terrestrial environments, where their behavior, toxic effects, and fate are still not completely predictable (Handy & Shaw, 2007; Maynard et al., 2006).

Although the experimental techniques like high throughput screening (HTS) allow to execute large batteries of toxicity assays, they are expensive as well as time-consuming. Further, it is becoming more and more tedious to manage the experimental determination of toxicity for progressively growing nano-particles space considering the possible combinations of nanoparticles showing different sizes, shapes, and chemical compositions, *etc.* In this scenario, the quantitative structure-activity/toxicity relationship (QSAR/QSTR) models (Puzyn et al., 2011; Roy, Kar, & Das, 2015) play an important role to enable cost-effective means of determining or screening potential nano hazards, and thus helps in reducing the burden of *in vitro/in vivo* assays. Moreover, QSAR models also help in understanding the structural features or factors that are responsible for their toxicity. Several nano-QSAR models have been already reported ((Gajewicz et al., 2015; Kar, Gajewicz, Puzyn, Roy, & Leszczynski, 2014; Mu et al., 2016; Pathakoti, Huang, Watts, He, & Hwang, 2014; Puzyn et al., 2011; Singh, Gupta, Kumar, & Mohan, 2014; Sizochenko et al., 2014; Toropov et al., 2012)) for predicting the toxicity of metal oxide nanoparticles. Although the prediction quality of these nano-QSTR models were within the acceptable range, these models were directed to single target only. Thus, it should be noted that the conventional QSAR models have the ability to predict the toxicity of nanoparticles against only one biological target and may not always take into consideration several important experimental parameters/conditions such as cell-line used, nanoparticle core size, shape, time of exposure, concentration exposed, *etc.* Therefore, in recent years, several researchers are focusing on developing multi-tasking QSAR models that are capable of handling multiple biological targets and/or multiple experimental conditions simultaneously. Several new approaches were reported in the literature, for instance, some authors have reported mtk-QSTR-perturbation modeling technique to develop multitasking nano-QSAR models to predict ecotoxicity, genotoxicity and/or cytotoxicity of nanoparticles (Halder, Melo, & Cordeiro, 2020; Kleandrova et al., 2014; Luan et al., 2014). While in another study (Basant & Gupta, 2017) the authors have modified the traditional QSAR methodology and reported an optimal multi target-QSTR model having a functional relationship between four different toxicity endpoints and corresponding predictors. Moreover, Choi et. al., (2018) reported a new methodology to develop a generalized nano-QSAR model by combining physicochemical properties, quantum-mechanical parameters, and different biological experimental conditions as descriptors/attributes, *etc.*

In the present work, the authors intended to develop a generalized quantitative structure-activity (/toxicity) relationship (QSAR/QSTR) models for predicting the cytotoxicity and genotoxicity of seven nanoparticles (namely, SiO₂, ZnO, TiO₂, CuO, Fe₂O₃, Fe₃O₄, Al₂O₃). Note that the study involves handling two different toxicity endpoints (cytotoxicity and genotoxicity), where the collected experimental response values were determined in different experimental conditions. Thus, to deal with such data we chose to build classification-based multi-tasking (*mtk*)-QSAR models (Kleandrova et al., 2014; Luan et al., 2014; Speck-Planche & Cordeiro, 2015) using Box-Jenkins moving average approach (Hill, Lewicki, & Lewicki, 2006). The Box-Jenkin's approach allows developing a multi-tasking QSAR model that can predict multiple responses, while taking into account the different experimental/theoretical conditions. The key difference in the present *mtk*-model compared to the previously reported mtk-QSAR models are, i) largest number of available data points are employed, ii) several important experimental conditions are considered while developing the model, iii) models

were developed using simple 2D-descriptors and periodic-based descriptors, and thus are not dependent on computationally expensive quantum-mechanics based descriptors.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Dataset Collection and Preparation

The dataset was collected from several reliable data repositories such as eNanoMapper (Jeliaskova et al., 2015), NANoREG (Gottardo et al., 2017), NanoDESK database (<http://sudoenanodesk.net/>) and also from several published literature (N. Chen et al., 2016; De Angelis et al., 2013; Fisichella et al., 2014; Ruizendaal et al., 2009; Choi, Ha, Trinh, Yoon, & Byun, 2018).

Initial raw data comprises 2491 data points with available toxicity information for several nanoparticle type, such as SiO₂, CuO, Fe₂O₃, Fe₃O₄, ZnO, TiO₂, Ag, Al₂O₃, Graphene and CeO₂. These data points represent the cytotoxicity and genotoxicity of these nanoparticles determined in different experimental protocols and conditions (i.e., exposure time, concentration exposed, the nanoparticle core sizes, cell lines). However, there was some missing information such as concentration exposed, nanoparticle size, etc. for some data points, as well as, several data points were found to be duplicates. The duplicates were likely since the data were collected from different sources as well as many data points represent experimental replicates. Notably, the data points were considered duplicates only if they were exactly identical in the following aspects: nanoparticle composition, studied toxicity (i.e., cytotoxicity or genotoxicity), experimental protocol, cell line, exposure time (in hours), concentration (in µg/ml), nanoparticle core size (in nanometer). Further, before removing the found duplicates, the duplicate analysis (Fourches, Muratov, & Tropsha, 2010) was performed in the following manner:

1. If the experimental toxicity (response) values of the duplicates are identical, then we have simply removed all the duplicates while keeping a unique data point in the dataset;
2. If the response values are not identical, then two situations were considered. In the first situation, if the response values of the duplicates were similar to each other such that all or most of the duplicates come under the same category (i.e., toxic or non-toxic), then the authors have removed all the duplicates except one and a curated response value was assigned to the data point kept. Here, the curated response value was computed by taking the average response values of the duplicates. In the second situation, where the activity values of the retrieved duplicates were highly different from each other (such that some of them are categorized as 'toxic', while some of them are categorized as 'non-toxic'), then such data points were removed. In this study, we found only 3 data points with ambiguous response values and thus were removed from the data set.

Finally, after removing the duplicates and the data points with the missing essential information, the resultant data set comprises 717 data points representing 7 metal oxides nanoparticles, namely, SiO₂, ZnO, TiO₂, CuO, Fe₂O₃, Fe₃O₄, Al₂O₃.

Descriptor Calculation

In the next step, several (1670) molecular 2D-descriptors were calculated using an *in-house* python script, ChemDes web platform (Dong et al., 2015) (<http://www.scbdd.com/chemdes/>), PaDEL-descriptor (Yap, 2011) and the periodic table-based descriptors (De, Kar, Roy, & Leszczynski, 2018). The computed descriptors include several classes of 2D-descriptors such as *atom centered, autocorrelation, burden eigenvalues, connectivity indices, constitutional, edge adjacency, eigenvalues, getaway, information indices, topological, topological charge, two dimensional, walk path counts, functional group, and simple descriptors derived from the periodic table information*. Here, the SMILES notations of metal oxides were utilized for the calculation of all 2D-descriptors except the periodic table-based descriptors. The periodic table-based descriptors were collected from the literature

(De et al., 2018). However, the final data set comprises 733 descriptors after removing the constant and inter-correlated descriptors using the variance cut-off (= 0.001) and correlation coefficient cut-off (= 0.99), respectively. Moreover, three experimental parameters, i.e., nanoparticle core size (*in nanometer*), concentration of nanoparticle exposed (*in µg/ml*), and exposure time (*in hours*) were also considered as descriptors while developing the models.

Model Development and Validation

In the present study, as mentioned earlier, the authors have employed Box-Jenkins moving average approach which allows to develop a multi-tasking QSAR model that can predict two endpoints, i.e., cytotoxicity and genotoxicity with different experimental/theoretical conditions simultaneously using a single QSAR model equation. Six experimental conditions (denoted as ‘*c*’) were considered for developing multi-tasking QSAR models: toxicity endpoints (denoted as ‘*Te*’, cytotoxicity, and genotoxicity), the experimental protocols (denoted as ‘*Ep*’, total 11 different protocols), exposure time (denoted as ‘*Et*’, time in hours), concentration exposed (denoted as ‘*Ce*’, concentrations in µg/ml), nanoparticle core size (denoted as ‘*Ns*’, measured in nanometer), cell lines (denoted as ‘*Cl*’, total 15 different cell lines). Additional details about the data set statistics, and the experimental conditions are provided in the supporting information available at <https://osf.io/cbdpx/> (online data repository). Note that the combination of these six experimental parameters define a unique experimental condition c_j , under which a nanoparticle is tested. Thus, c_j is represented as an ontology with the form $c_j \rightarrow (Te, Ep, Et, Ce, Ns, Cl)$. Further, each data point in the data set was annotated to belong to 1 of 2 possible classes, namely positive [$TE_i(c_j) = P$] or negative [$TE_i(c_j) = N$]. Here, $TE_i(c_j)$ is a binary variable that symbolizes the toxicological effect (*TE*) of the i^{th} nanoparticle under the experimental condition c_j . The class assignments were performed according to predefined cutoff values (L. Chen, Peijnenburg, de Haan, & Rietjens, 2019; López-García, Lehocký, Humpolíček, & Sába, 2014; Sharma et al., 2010), as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Pre-defined cut-off values for classifying the data into toxic and non-toxic category

Toxicity Endpoint (Measurement Type)	Pre-Defined Cut-Off Values	
	Non-Toxic (Negative)	Toxic (Positive)
Cytotoxicity (% cell viability)	>80	≤ 80
Genotoxicity (% DNA in the tail)	<10	≥ 10

All the task related to *mtk*-QSAR model development using Box-Jenkin’s moving average approach was performed using *QSAR-Co software* (Ambure, Halder, GonzálezDíaz, & Cordeiro, 2019) (freely available to download at <https://sites.google.com/view/qsar-co>). Notably, once the prepared input file with essential information (i.e., *compound ID*, *experimental conditions*, *response class*, and *descriptors*) is provided to the QSAR-Co software, using the software one can perform all the steps required for the QSAR model development such as computing modified descriptor set (based on *Box-Jenkins moving average approach*), data pre-treatment (removes constant and inter-correlated descriptors), data set division, variable selection, model development, validation and determination of the applicability domain. In this study, the data set was divided into a training set (70%) and a test set (30%) using the Random approach available in the QSAR-Co software. The training set was employed for the development and selection of the optimum model whereas the test set was exclusively utilized to validate the model. The genetic algorithm (GA) and best subset

selection (BSS) were utilized as variable/feature selection techniques. The final *mtk*-models were developed using two machine learning techniques implemented in QSAR-Co software, *i.e.*, linear discriminant analysis (LDA) (Snedecor & Cochran, 1989; Venkatasubramanian & Sundaram, 2002) and Random Forest (RF) (Breiman, 2001).

The parameters/setting used in the GA were as follows, (a) the total number of iteration/generations: 1000, (b) model equation length: 8, (c) mutation probability: 0.3, (d) the initial number of model equations generated: 500, (e) number of model equations selected in each generation: 150. Both Mathew's correlation coefficient (MCC) and Wilks lambda (λ) parameter (Wilks, 1932) were employed to compute the fitness score in the GA, which is then utilized to select the best model in each generation. A set of top descriptors were selected based on the results of the GA (*i.e.*, from the models with good fitness scores), which were then utilized in BSS for finding the best possible LDA model as well as to derive a RF model.

The optimum LDA and RF models were evaluated and selected based on the qualitative validation metrics computed for the training set and then the selected models were externally validated using the test set. Thus, qualitative validation metrics (Fawcett, 2006) such as accuracy, precision, sensitivity, specificity, MCC, F-score were calculated for both the training and test sets for performing internal and external validation, respectively. Further, receiver operating characteristics (ROC) curve (Fawcett, 2006) along with the area under the curve (AUC) were checked to determine the discriminating ability of the developed LDA and RF models. The robustness of the LDA model was also evaluated using Y-randomization test (Fisher, 1960), where the dependent variable (response class) of the training set was scrambled 50 times and the models were built again that resulted in 50 random LDA models. Further, Wilks λ parameter of the original model was compared to the Wilks λ values of 50 random models to circumvent the possibility that the original LDA model was developed by chance. Finally, the domain of applicability was determined for both LDA and RF models using the standardization approach (Roy, Kar, & Ambure, 2015).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) Model

Among all models generated from the BSS algorithm (*i.e.*, utilizing all possible combinations of pre-screened 23 top descriptors obtained from the GA), the best LDA model was selected with least Wilks (λ)_{Train} and highest MCC_{Train}. The following Equation 1 shows the standardized coefficients for the selected descriptors in the selected optimal LDA model:

$$\begin{aligned} TE_i(c_i) = & (0.679 \times \text{HallKierAlpha_Ce}) + (2.097 \times \text{MATS2m_Ns}) \\ & - (0.372 \times \text{ExposureTime_Ce}) + (0.907 \times \text{CrippenMR_Ep}) + (2.195 \times \text{AATS0Z_Ns}) \dots \\ & - (2.687 \times \text{LogEE_m_Ns}) - (0.344 \times \text{Conc. Exposed_Ep}) - (0.353 \times \text{SM1_se_Cl}) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

The standardized coefficient values in Equation 1 give an idea about the contribution of each descriptor towards the non-toxicity of the nanoparticles, for instance, in this case, the descriptor 'LogEE_m_Ns' has the highest (*negative*) contribution (*coefficient value* = -2.687) towards the *non-toxicity* of the nanoparticles. Notably, five experimental conditions, namely, concentration exposed, core size of nanoparticle, exposure time, experimental protocols, and cell lines (except 'toxicity endpoints') were found to play an important role in toxicity class prediction.

Here, we will briefly describe the meaning and contribution (along with the source) of each descriptor that are selected in the final LDA model (summarized in Table 2):

- **HallKierAlpha_Ce:** The Kier and Hall (L. H. Hall & Kier, 1991) defined molecular shape indices that compare the molecular graph with minimal and maximal molecular graphs depending on

Table 2. Symbols and definitions for the descriptors selected in the mtk-QSAR (LDA and RF) models

Descriptor [Type]	Brief Description	Descriptor Source (Reference)
HallKierAlpha_Ce [2D Topological]	'HallKierAlpha' represents the Hall-Kier alpha value for a molecule. '_Ce' suggests that this descriptor also considers (and depends on) concentration of nanoparticles exposed.	RDKit (Landrum, 2013)
MATS2m_Ns [2D Autocorrelation]	The 'MATS2m' stands for Moran autocorrelation - lag 2/weighted by atomic masses. '_Ns' suggests that this descriptor also considers (and depends on) the core size of nanoparticles.	Mordred descriptors (Moriwaki, Tian, Kawashita, & Takagi, 2018)
ExposureTime_Ce	The 'ExposureTime' stands for exposure time (in hours) during the experiments. '_Ce' suggests that this descriptor also considers (and depends on) concentration of nanoparticles exposed.	Experimental data
CrippenMR_Ep [Crippen Descriptor]	The 'CrippenMR' stands for Crippen's molar refractivity. '_Ep' suggests that this descriptor also considers (and depends on) the experimental protocol employed.	PaDEL-descriptor (Yap, 2011)
AATS0Z_Ns [2D Autocorrelation]	AATS0Z stands for averaged moreau-broto autocorrelation of lag 0 weighted by atomic number. '_Ns' suggests that this descriptor also considers (and depends on) the core size of nanoparticles.	MordredDescriptors (Moriwaki et al., 2018)
LogEE_m_Ns [2D matrix-based]	LogEE_m stands for 2D matrix-based descriptors derived from the Barysz matrix weighted by mass. '_Ns' suggests that this descriptor also considers (and depends on) the core size of nanoparticles.	MordredDescriptors (Moriwaki et al., 2018)
Conc. Exposed_Ep	The 'Conc. Exposed' stands for concentration of nanoparticles (in µg/ml) exposed during the experiments. '_Ep' suggests that this descriptor also considers (and depends on) the experimental protocol employed.	Experimental data
SMI_se_CI [spectral moment]	SMI_se stands for spectral moment of order 1 from the Barysz matrix weighted by sanderson electronegativity. '_CI' suggests that this descriptor also considers (and depends on) the cell line used.	MordredDescriptors (Moriwaki et al., 2018)

the order (1, 2 or 3), where each order represent structural information such as count of atoms (path of length 1) and the presence of cycle (*order 1*), branching (*order 2*) and counts of paths of length 3 (*order 3*). The 'HallKierAlpha' descriptor represents the modified shape indices that also considers the contribution of covalent radii and hybridization states to the shape of the molecule. In the LDA model, this descriptor was found to positively contribute to the nontoxicity of the nanoparticles (thus, negatively contributing to the toxicity of nanoparticles), while the modified descriptor 'HallKierAlpha_Ce' also considers and depends on the concentration of nanoparticle exposed;

- **MATS2m_Ns:** Moran autocorrelation are 2D-autocorrelation descriptors that explain how the values of certain functions, at intervals equal to the lag, are correlated. Here, the descriptor 'MATS2m' represents a lag in terms of the topological distance (where, $d = 2$) and the 'atomic masses' is the function that was correlated. This descriptor provides a global and dimension-limited code, while addressing the topology of the structures together with the association with identified physicochemical properties (Velázquez-Libera, Caballero, Toropova, & Toropov, 2019). In this study, it showed a positive correlation with the nontoxicity of the nanoparticles, while the modified descriptor 'MATS2m_Ns' also depends on the core size of nanoparticles;
- **CrippenMR_Ep:** CrippenMR descriptor represents the molar refractivity of the nanoparticle that is computed based on a group contribution, where the individual molar refractivity contributions for 150 atom types were defined by Ghose-Crippen (Ghose, Pritchett, & Crippen, 1988). Thus, CrippenMR can be calculated as the sum of the contributions of each of the atoms in the molecules. Here, the molar refractivity was found to be positively correlated to the nontoxicity of the nanoparticles, while it also considers and depends on the experimental protocol employed;
- **AATS0Z_Ns:** AATS0Z is the averaged Moreau-Broto 2D autocorrelation (Broto, Moreau, & Vandicke, 1984) of lag 0 weighted by atomic number. Like MATS2m, it also describes how a property is distributed along with the topological structure. Here, it is also positively contributing

to the nontoxicity of the nanoparticles, while *AATSOZ_Ns* descriptor also considers and depends on the core size of the nanoparticles;

- **LogEE_m_Ns:** *LogEE_m* is a 2D matrix-based descriptor. It is defined as the logarithmic coefficient sum of the last eigenvector from the Barysz matrix and is weighted by mass (Barysz, Jashari, Lall, Srivastava, & Trinajstić, 1983). This descriptor was found to negatively contribute to the nontoxicity of the nanoparticles (thus, positively contributing to the toxicity of nanoparticles), while this descriptor also considers and depends on the core size of the nanoparticles;
- **SMI_se_CI:** *SMI_se* descriptor represents the spectral moment of order 1 from the Barysz matrix and is weighted by Sanderson electronegativities (Barysz et al., 1983). It is negatively contributing to the nontoxicity of the nanoparticles (thus, positively contributing to the toxicity of nanoparticles), while this descriptor also considers and depends on the cell line used.

Thus, both experimental conditions and the selected structural features (descriptors) play an important role in predicting the toxicity of studied nanoparticles. To understand it better, three cases are discussed utilizing the samples from the dataset and relevant information is provided in Table 3. The first case (example 1 in Table 3) involves nine data points (i.e., B028 to B036) that represents the same nanoparticle, i.e., CuO, however, one can notice that data points (B028 to B032) are non toxic while B033 to B036 are toxic. Here, all the experimental parameters (*assay, cell line, exposure time, core nanoparticle size*) are the same for all the data points except *concentration exposed* (*Ce*, dose). The data points (B028 to B032) with $Ce \leq 5\mu\text{g/ml}$ are non toxic, while data points with $Ce > 5\mu\text{g/ml}$ are toxic. It is important to note that this information is successfully encoded in the descriptor 'HallKierAlpha_Ce' (modified descriptor, see the values in Table 3), whereas the original descriptor value is the same for all these data points (*representing CuO*), as expected. This example shows the importance of experimental parameters in predicting the toxicity of nanoparticles. The second case (example 2 in Table 3) also shows the importance of another experimental parameter i.e., core size of nanoparticles (*Ns*) in toxicity prediction. The data points (A027, A023, A050) represent the same nanoparticle, i.e. SiO₂, however, A027 and A050 with core size 19.2 nm and 109.8 nm are non toxic, while A023 with size 31.4 nm is toxic. Here, the size information is successfully encoded in the modified descriptor 'MATS2m_Ns' (see the descriptor values in Table 3) and thus contribute to classification or prediction of toxicity. The third case (example 3 in Table 3) shows the importance of a descriptor (structural feature) in the prediction of toxicity. The data points B077 and B033 represent two nanoparticles, i.e., Fe₃O₄ and CuO, where Fe₃O₄ is non toxic and CuO is toxic. Notably here all the experimental parameters (*assay, cell line, exposure time, concentration exposed*) for both the data points are the same with very little difference in the *core sizes* (see the sizes in Table 3), which means that there should not be a significant influence of experimental parameters in the toxicity of these nanoparticles. Thus, this case is a good example to observe the role of descriptors to describe the toxicity, for instance, in this example, HallKierAlpha descriptor (see the original descriptor values in Table 3) representing shape of the nanoparticles explains the toxicity very well and is positively contributing to the non-toxicity of nanoparticles.

Additionally, the classification/discriminant function that can be employed to predict the class of query or newly designed nanoparticle is mentioned in Table 4.

The optimal values obtained for statistical parameters such as accuracy, precision, sensitivity, specificity, F-measure and Mathew's correlation coefficient (MCC) are indicative of good discriminatory power of the developed model (see Table 5). A similar performance was shown by the LDA model for the test set compounds. Thus, it can be concluded that the developed LDA *mtk*-QSAR model is aptly capable of differentiating between toxic and non-toxic nanoparticles.

To further evaluate the statistical significance of the developed model, ROC curves (Fawcett, 2006) (see Figure 1) were plotted for both the training and test sets employing the 10-fold cross-validation approach. The area under the ROC curve (AUC) values (see Table 5) obtained for both the training set (= 0.928) and the test set (= 0.920) shows that the model is a statistically significant

Table 3. Demonstrating the role of experimental conditions and descriptors in prediction of toxicity of studied nanoparticles using few examples

Example 1					
Nano ID	Common Parameters	Ce	Response Class	HallKierAlpha (Original Descriptor)	HallKierAlpha_Ce (Modified Descriptor)
B028*	^{Nt} CuO ^{Te} Cyto-toxicity ^{Ep} MTT reduction assay ^{Ct} HCMEC ^{Et} 12 ^{Ns} 46.3	0.001	Non Toxic	0.319	0.199
B029		0.01	Non Toxic	0.319	0.199
B030*		0.1	Non Toxic	0.319	0.199
B031		1	Non Toxic	0.319	0.502
B032		5	Non Toxic	0.319	0.133
B033		10	Toxic	0.319	-0.005
B034		20	Toxic	0.319	-0.014
B035		50	Toxic	0.319	-0.041
B036*		100	Toxic	0.319	-0.034
Example 2					
Nano ID	Common Parameters	Ns	Response Class	MATS2m	MATS2m_Ns
A027*	^{Nt} SiO₂ ^{Te} Cyto-toxicity ^{Ep} MTT reduction assay ^{Ct} CaCo-2 ^{Et} 4 ^{Ce} 600	19.2	Non Toxic	0.405	0.405
A023*		31.4	Toxic	0.405	0.000
A050*		109.8	Non Toxic	0.405	0.405
Example 3					
Nano ID	Common Parameters	Nt (Ns)	Response Class	HallKierAlpha (Original Descriptor)	HallKierAlpha_Ce (Modified Descriptor)
B077*	^{Te} Cyto-toxicity ^{Ep} MTT reduction assay ^{Ct} HCMEC ^{Et} 12 ^{Ce} 10	Fe₃O₄ (46.8)	Non Toxic	1.078	0.754
B033		CuO (46.3)	Toxic	0.319	-0.005

*: data point present in the test set

Nt: Nanoparticle type

Te: Toxicity endpoint

Ep: Experimental protocol

Ct: Cell line

HCMEC: Human Cerebral Microvascular Endothelial Cell Line

CaCo-2: Human epithelial colorectal adenocarcinoma cells

Et: Exposure time

Ns: nanoparticle size (core)

Ce: concentration exposed

classifier since those values are considerably higher than that of a random classifier ($=0.5$). Moreover, the Y-randomization test (Fisher, 1960) inferred that the present *mtk*-QSAR model is not developed by chance. The Y-randomization test results are illustrated in Figure 2, where one can observe that the Wilk's lambda values for all 50 random models (average $\lambda_{\text{random}} = 0.984$) are significantly higher than the original value for λ_{Train} (i.e., 0.58). Finally, the applicability domain was determined using

Table 4. Classification or discriminant functions

Classification/Discriminant Functions	Negative (Non-Toxic)	Positive (Toxic)
	p=0.723	p=0.277
Intercept	-2.095	-1.287
HallKierAlpha_Ce	3.898	0.073
MATS2m_Ns	9.071	0.051
ExposureTime_Ce	-0.037	0.003
CrippenMR_Ep	0.708	-0.002
AATSOZ_Ns	1.886	0.002
LogEE_m_Ns	-6.211	-0.017
Conc. Exposed_Ep	-0.007	0.000
SM1_se_Cl	-1.432	-0.018

Table 5. Performance of the mtk-QSAR models (LDA and RF)

Classification Model Evaluation Parameters	LDA		RF		
	Training Set	Test Set	Training Set	Training Set (10-Cv ^d)	Test Set
<i>NC^a Positive</i>	139	53	139	139	53
<i>NC^a Negative</i>	363	162	363	363	162
<i>True Positive</i>	125	50	136	122	49
<i>False Positive</i>	40	21	5	21	6
<i>True Negative</i>	323	141	358	342	156
<i>False Negative</i>	14	3	3	17	4
<i>Accuracy (%)</i>	89.24	88.83	98.41	92.43	94.42
<i>Precision (%)</i>	75.76	70.42	96.45	85.30	87.27
<i>Sensitivity (%)</i>	89.93	94.34	97.84	87.77	90.57
<i>Specificity (%)</i>	88.98	87.04	98.62	94.21	95.70
<i>F-measure</i>	0.82	0.81	97.14	0.865	0.89
<i>MCC^b</i>	0.752	0.746	96.04	0.813	0.85
<i>AUROC^c</i>	0.928	0.920	0.999	0.981	0.961
<i>Wilk's Lambda</i>	0.58	-	0.58	0.58	-

^aNC: Number of cases

^bMCC: Mathew correlation coefficient

^cAUROC: Area under the receiver operating characteristic curve

^d10-CV: 10-fold cross-validation results

the standardization approach available in the QSAR-Co software. The standardization approach (Roy, Kar, & Ambure, 2015) showed that 5 (out of total 502) data points of the training set and 6 (out of total 215) data points of the test set were found as possible outliers and outside the applicability domain, respectively.

Figure 1. ROC (using 10-fold cross-validation) plots for the best LDA model

Figure 2. Y-randomization test results for the developed LDA model

Random Forest (RF) Model

The RF technique was also utilized to build a non-linear classification-based mtk-QSAR model using the same training and test sets that were employed to build the LDA model. It was also developed using QSAR-Co software, which utilizes the *Weka version 3.9.3 library* (M. Hall et al., 2009) for RF calculations. Though the authors initially utilized all 23 top descriptors obtained from the GA for development of the RF model; however, later they noticed that the model quality was similar to the RF model developed using the same 8 descriptors that were present in the best LDA model. Thus, the RF model with only 8 descriptors was finally chosen as the optimal RF model. The default RF

parameters of QSAR-Co were chosen, and a 10-fold cross-validation procedure performed to assess the internal predictability of the model. The resultant statistical parameters of the derived model are provided in Table 5, and as typically anticipated the overall statistical prediction quality of the RF model was found to be superior to that of the LDA model. However, the LDA model has better sensitivity values (i.e., less false negatives) for both training and test sets when compared to the RF model and thus are better at predicting positives or toxic nanoparticles, while the RF model has better precision value (i.e., less false positives) and thus is better in predicting negatives or non-toxic nanoparticles. Thus, employing both models would be always beneficial to perform consensus predictions for query or newly designed nanoparticles. Further, Figure 3 shows the plots of the corresponding ROC curves

Figure 3. ROC (using 10-fold cross-validation) plots for the derived RF model

for the RF model, and the AUC values (see Table 5) for both the training set (= 0.981) and the test set (= 0.961) shows that the model has significant discriminatory power. Please note that since the same descriptors (*selected in LDA*) were used to develop the RF model, thus the results of applicability domain using the Standardization approach (*as discussed earlier for the LDA model*) will remain the same. Moreover, the contribution of each descriptor was identified based on the average impurity decrease per attribute over the trees (*computed by default in the QSAR-Co software*) and it was found in the following order: SM1_se_Cl > ExposureTime_Ce > Conc. Exposed_Ep > AATS0Z_Ns > CrippenMR_Ep > HallKierAlpha_Ce > LogEE_m_Ns > MATS2m_Ns.

Note that all the details relevant to the model development such as input dataset information, final models (LDA and RF), results of Y-randomization test and the applicability domain study are available at <https://osf.io/cbdpx/> (online data repository) as supporting information.

In-Depth Analysis of Predictive Performance of Developed Multi-Tasking (Generalized) LDA and RF Models

The authors have performed a detailed analysis of prediction performance of the developed generalized LDA and RF models to understand the performance of models with respect to each toxicity endpoint, nanoparticles type, experimental protocols, and cell lines employed. Since several experimental conditions were involved in the model development, it was really interesting to evaluate and check the prediction quality of developed models considering each experimental condition as separate case, for instance, to evaluate how the LDA and RF models perform for cytotoxicity endpoint and genotoxicity endpoint separately. Similarly, the authors have checked how the models performed for

different nanoparticle types, experimental protocols, as well as cell lines. The predictive performance is simply evaluated by computing the % correct prediction (both positives and negatives combined) under each case and reported in Table 6. As observed from the analysis, both the models performed efficiently in all the studied cases, since in most cases the percentages of correct predictions were higher than 80 – 90%.

Table 6. Predictive performance of the mtk-(generalized) QSAR models (LDA and RF) with respect to toxicity endpoints, nanoparticle types, experimental protocols, and cell lines

Cases Studied	#N _{data}	LDA (in %*)	RF (in %*)
Entire Dataset	717	89.12	97.21
Nanoparticle Type			
<i>SiO₂</i>	127	88.98	97.64
<i>TiO₂</i>	197	95.43	98.98
<i>ZnO</i>	265	80.75	94.34
<i>Al₂O₃</i>	18	100.00	100.00
<i>CuO</i>	18	83.33	100.00
<i>Fe₂O₃</i>	18	100.00	100.00
<i>Fe₃O₄</i>	74	98.65	100.00
Toxicity Endpoint			
<i>Cytotoxicity</i>	702	89.32	97.29
<i>GenoToxicity</i>	15	80.00	93.33
Experimental Protocols			
<i>MTS Assay</i>	134	93.28	98.51
<i>AlamarBlue Assay</i>	29	82.76	100.00
<i>MTT reduction assay</i>	378	87.57	95.77
<i>DNA Strand breaks assay</i>	15	80.00	93.33
<i>Natural Red Assay</i>	2	100.00	100.00
<i>Lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) Cytotoxicity Assay</i>	4	75.00	100.00
<i>Neutral Red Uptake (NRU) cytotoxicity assay</i>	60	88.33	100.00
<i>Annexin V/PI Apoptosis Assay</i>	6	100.00	100.00
<i>ATP assay</i>	12	100.00	100.00
<i>CyQUANT LDH Cytotoxicity Assay</i>	5	80.00	100.00
<i>Cell Counting Kit-8</i>	72	93.06	98.61
Cell lines			
<i>Human epithelial colorectal adenocarcinoma cells</i>	115	84.35	99.13
<i>Human colon adenocarcinoma cell line HT29</i>	8	62.50	100.00
<i>Human Cerebral Microvascular Endothelial Cell Line</i>	90	95.56	98.89
<i>Adenocarcinoma human alveolar basal epithelial cells</i>	227	89.43	95.15

continued on following page

Table 6. Continued

Cases Studied	#N _{data}	LDA (in %*)	RF (in %*)
Entire Dataset	717	89.12	97.21
<i>Normal human bronchial epithelial cells</i>	74	93.24	98.65
<i>Human mesothelial cell line</i>	8	62.50	75.00
<i>Human neuroblastoma</i>	119	90.76	98.32
<i>Human mammary epithelial cell line</i>	2	100.00	100.00
<i>Diploid human cell line composed of fibroblasts</i>	2	100.00	100.00
<i>HeLA (cervical cancer cells) cell line</i>	2	100.00	100.00
<i>human fetal hepatocyte cell line</i>	12	100.00	100.00
<i>Lung tissue of a male Chinese hamster.</i>	24	79.17	95.83
<i>Murine tumours induced with Abelson leukaemia virus</i>	10	90.00	100.00
<i>human colon cancer cell line SW480</i>	14	92.86	100.00
<i>Human olfactory neurosphere-derived cells</i>	10	70.00	90.00

Number of datapoints in each case

* % correct predictions (both positives and negatives combined)

CONCLUSION

To summarize the work, we have developed generalized classification-based QSAR models to study two toxicity endpoints of our interest, namely, cytotoxicity and genotoxicity for a selected class of nanoparticles. The authors would like to emphasize that this is a first attempt of reporting a generalized model suitable for predicting both cytotoxicity and genotoxicity of metal oxides nanoparticles with the largest number of data points when compared to other reported generalized models developed for prediction of either genotoxicity (Halder, Melo, & Cordeiro, 2020) or cytotoxicity (Choi, Ha, Trinh, Yoon, & Byun, 2018) endpoints of metal oxide nanoparticles. Here, the generalized or multi-tasking (*mtk*)-QSAR models were developed using the Box-Jenkins moving average approach, which allowed the authors to merge the experimental response values that are determined in different experimental/theoretical conditions against two toxicity endpoints. The developed *mtk*-QSAR models can predict dual toxicity endpoints (*with diverse experimental conditions*) using a single QSAR model. In the present study, the models were developed using two machine learning techniques, i.e., LDA and RF. The computed internal (training set) and external (test set) validation metrics showed that the developed models have significant discriminatory power and are robust. The applicability domain of LDA and RF models were checked using the standardization, and the outliers (in the training set) as well as the data points that are outside the applicability domain (in the test set) were reported accordingly. Further, the RF model was found superior in overall prediction quality as compared to LDA. However as discussed earlier, the LDA model was found to be better at predicting positives or toxic nanoparticles, while the RF model was found to be better at predicting negatives or non-toxic nanoparticles. Thus, keeping both models will provide an opportunity to perform consensus predictions, which should significantly improve the quality of predictions. Further, LDA models are linear models that are simple to understand and are usually faster in screening large size databases as compared to the RF model. Nevertheless, the authors suggest that in a situation when only single model predictions are preferred, the RF model will always be the most appropriate choice due to superior prediction quality. Finally, the developed *mtk*-nano-QSAR models can be efficiently utilized for predicting the cytotoxicity and genotoxicity of newly designed nanoparticles or to fill the gap of

existing nanoparticles. These generalized models will surely assist us to comprehend the impact of nanoparticles on human health.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This study has been partially financed by the Instituto Valenciano de Competitividad Empresarial, (IVACE, <http://www.ivace.es/>) through the program “PIDI-CV” project number IMIDTA/2018/24 (Project acronym: AlerTox). P.A. acknowledges the funding assistance from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 845373”.

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